

Transferosome-assisted transdermal delivery of rivaroxaban: formulation and evaluation

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Abstract

Rivaroxaban (RIV) is an orally active, selective, direct factor Xa inhibitor used for the prevention and treatment of venous thromboembolism, stroke prevention in non-valvular atrial fibrillation, and other thromboembolic disorders. This research developed RIV-loaded transferosomes as a non-invasive option for individuals who cannot administer oral anticoagulants. Twenty RIV transferosomal formulations (F1–F20) were prepared by the rotary evaporation–sonication method using lecithin and various edge activators (Soluplus, Span 65, Span 80, and Tween 20) at different phospholipid-to-edge activator ratios. RIV transferosomal formulations (F1–F20) were evaluated for drug content, entrapment efficiency, vesicle size, polydispersity index, and pH. The lead transferosomal RIV formulation (F4) showed $93.6\% \pm 0.36$ entrapment efficiency, $97\% \pm 0.43$ drug content, a vesicle size of 98.36 ± 2 nm, and a pH of 6.69 ± 0.76 . F4 attained a drug release of $97.8\% \pm 0.72$ after 24 h and markedly improved ex vivo skin permeability relative to an RIV suspension ($p < 0.05$). F4 had a zeta potential of -24.16 mV and a deformability index of 9.6 ± 0.34 . The absence of drug–excipient incompatibilities was confirmed by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), and powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD). Field-emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM) demonstrated smooth, spherical vesicles. F4 demonstrated enhanced ex vivo skin permeation and suitable physicochemical characteristics.

Keywords

edge activator, phospholipid, rivaroxaban, Soluplus, transferosomes

Introduction

The transdermal administration of drugs offers several advantages over conventional oral and parenteral routes, including avoidance of first-pass metabolism, maintenance of relatively constant plasma drug levels, reduction of dosing frequency, and improved patient compliance. It also has the potential to minimize systemic adverse effects and gastrointestinal irritation associated with oral dosage forms, which is important in chronic therapies (Zhou et al. 2018). Transferosomes are ultra-deformable vesicular

nanocarriers composed of phospholipids and an edge activator, typically a single-chain surfactant. These flexible vesicles contain an aqueous core surrounded by a lipid bilayer and are specifically designed to penetrate the stratum corneum by squeezing through narrow intercellular pores that are smaller than their diameter without losing their structural integrity (Rajendran et al. 2026). Owing to their deformability, transferosomes have been widely investigated for enhancing dermal and transdermal delivery of both hydrophilic and lipophilic drugs (Gupta and Kumar 2021). The first major constituent of the transfero-

some is the amphipathic component, the vesicle-forming element that composes the lipid bilayer. Common examples of amphipathic components include phospholipids. Lecithin and soy phosphatidylcholine are the two most often used natural and synthetic lipid components in transferosomes. Phospholipids are essential in the formulation of transferosomes since they influence zeta potential, trapping efficiency, vesicle size, and vesicle permeability properties (Abdulbaqi et al. 2016). Edge activators are the second main ingredient in transferosomes, with a content range of 10%–25%. These compounds soften the biocompatible bilayer of the vesicles, thereby enhancing their permeation and flexibility. The main types include non-ionic surfactants, such as Tween and Span; bile salts, such as sodium cholate and sodium deoxycholate; and biocompatible esters (Matharoo et al. 2024). The nature of the edge activator used in the formulation of transferosome vesicles affects their deformability, trapping efficiency, and zeta potential. This may be due to their different chemical structures (Firoznejhad et al. 2022). Tweens and Spans are non-ionic surfactants; they have no inherent ionic interaction affinity and are widely compatible and stable in many fluid systems, including fresh water, saline water, mild acids, and alkaline solutions, and they do not react with ionic ingredients and charged substances. Spans are sorbitan esters that are manufactured from the dehydration of sorbitol through an esterification reaction with fatty acids. The size and length of the fatty acid molecules used determine the hydrophilic–hydrophobic balance (HLB) and the solubility of the surfactant in polar and nonpolar solvents. Further esterification with fatty acids results in polyesters (Abu Zaid et al. 2025). The HLB value decreases with increasing degrees of esterification and size of the fatty acid molecules (Abdulbaqi et al. 2016). Span 80 (sorbitan monooleate) has an HLB value of 4.3. Span 65 (sorbitan tristearate) has an HLB of 2.1. Tweens are produced by the ethoxylation of Spans to increase the HLB range and enhance hydrophilic solubility (Apenten and Zhu 1996). Tweens are soluble or dispersible in water and dilute solutions of electrolytes. The solubility of Tweens in aqueous solution increases with the degree of ethoxylation. However, for a fixed degree of ethoxylation and esterification, aqueous solubility decreases as the size and molecular weight of the fatty acid increase (Abojaladi and Kelland 2016; Park and Sa 2026). Tween 20 (polyoxyethylene sorbitan monolaurate) is a non-ionic surfactant that has an HLB of 16.7. More recently, amphiphilic polymers such as Soluplus, a graft copolymer of polyvinyl caprolactam–polyvinyl acetate–polyethylene glycol, have been explored as novel edge-activating components due to their ability to self-assemble, enhance drug solubility, and modulate membrane interactions, offering a distinct physicochemical profile compared with conventional small-molecule surfactants and adding a clear element of formulation novelty (Mali et al. 2025). Rivaroxaban (RIV) is an orally active, selective, direct factor Xa inhibitor used for the prevention and treat-

ment of venous thromboembolism, stroke prevention in non-valvular atrial fibrillation, and other thromboembolic disorders (Wang et al. 2023). Despite its proven efficacy and favorable pharmacokinetic profile, oral RIV therapy may be problematic in patients with persistent vomiting, dysphagia, impaired consciousness, or poor adherence, in whom oral administration is difficult or impossible. For such patient populations, a non-invasive transdermal delivery system could provide a valuable alternative to parenteral anticoagulants and improve therapeutic outcomes. Several transfersomal formulations have been reported to enhance the transdermal delivery of various drugs, including antifungal, antihypertensive, and other cardiovascular agents (Matharoo et al. 2024). However, limited work has been performed on developing RIV-loaded transferosomes for systemic transdermal delivery, and, to the best of current knowledge, Soluplus has not been systematically explored as an edge activator in RIV transfersomal systems. Therefore, this study was undertaken to formulate and characterize Soluplus-based RIV transferosomes, to compare them with transferosomes containing other conventional edge activators, and to evaluate their *in vitro* and *ex vivo* performance as a potential non-invasive anticoagulant delivery platform.

Materials and methods

Materials

Rivaroxaban was purchased from Macklin Pharmaceutical Co., Ltd. (China). Lecithin was purchased from Lyan Pharmaceuticals, China. Soluplus, Span 65, Span 80, Tween 20, chloroform, sodium lauryl sulfate (SLS), and methanol were supplied by LOBA CHEMIE PVT. LTD. All other reagents and solvents were of analytical grade and used as received. Deionized water was used throughout the study.

Methods

Determination of lambda maximum (λ max) of rivaroxaban

A UV-visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu, Japan) was used to analyze a stock solution (100 μ g/mL), which was prepared by dissolving 10 mg of RIV in 100 mL of methanol. Another stock solution (100 μ g/mL) was prepared by dissolving 10 mg of RIV in 100 mL of PBS at pH 7.4 + 1% w/v SLS. The wavelength range of the analysis was 200–400 nm. The λ max of RIV was recorded (Borse et al. 2022).

Calibration curve construction of rivaroxaban

Calibration curves for RIV were generated using two different solvents: methanol and PBS pH 7.4 + 1% w/v SLS. The process involved extracting an appropriate quantity from the stock solution and transferring it into a volumetric flask with a capacity of 10 mL. The flask was then filled

up to the 10 mL mark with the corresponding solvent, resulting in the preparation of working solutions of RIV (2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16, 18, and 20 µg/mL). The drug absorbance in each solvent was then measured using a spectrophotometer (Shimadzu, Japan) at the estimated λ max of RIV. The resulting data were then plotted versus concentration to create the calibration curve (Borse et al. 2022).

Rivaroxaban-loaded transfersome preparation

Twenty RIV-loaded transfersomal formulations (F1–F20) were prepared using the rotary evaporation–sonication method. Briefly, RIV (10 mg), lecithin (200 mg), and the respective edge activator (Soluplus, Span 65, Span 80, or Tween 20) at different lecithin/edge activator ratios (95:5, 90:10, 85:15, 80:20, and 75:25 w/w) were dissolved in a 12 mL organic solvent mixture of methanol and chloroform (1:2 v/v) in a round-bottom flask. The organic phase was

evaporated under reduced pressure at 90 rpm and 40–45 °C using a rotary evaporator (Buchi R-300 Rotavapor, Germany) until a thin, uniform lipid film was formed on the inner wall of the flask. The resulting thin film was left overnight at ambient temperature for complete solvent evaporation. Subsequently, 10 mL of preheated phosphate-buffered saline (PBS, pH 7.4) maintained at 55 °C was added to the dried film, and the dispersion was hydrated under continued rotation at 55 °C for 60 min to obtain a crude transfersomal dispersion. The resultant dispersion was then probe-sonicated (QSONICA, Q 500 Sonicator, USA) at 30% power in a pulsatile manner (15-second sonication with a 5-second pause) for 10 min to obtain nanosized vesicles. The resulting transfersomal dispersion was filtered (0.22 µm) to remove aggregates and stored at 3–8 °C until further characterization (Ahad et al. 2017). RIV-loaded transfersomal formulations are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. RIV-loaded transfersome compositions.

Formulations	PH/ EA%	Lecithin (mg)	Rivaroxaban (mg)	Soluplus (mg)	Span 65 (mg)	Span 80 (mg)	Tween 20 (mg)
F1	95/5	200	10	10	–	–	–
F2	90/10	200	10	20	–	–	–
F3	85/15	200	10	30	–	–	–
F4	80/20	200	10	40	–	–	–
F5	75/25	200	10	50	–	–	–
F6	95/5	200	10	–	10	–	–
F7	90/10	200	10	–	20	–	–
F8	85/15	200	10	–	30	–	–
F9	80/20	200	10	–	40	–	–
F10	75/25	200	10	–	50	–	–
F11	95/5	200	10	–	–	10	–
F12	90/10	200	10	–	–	20	–
F13	85/15	200	10	–	–	30	–
F14	80/20	200	10	–	–	40	–
F15	75/25	200	10	–	–	50	–
F16	95/5	200	10	–	–	–	10
F17	90/10	200	10	–	–	–	20
F18	85/15	200	10	–	–	–	30
F19	80/20	200	10	–	–	–	40
F20	75/25	200	10	–	–	–	50

PH: lecithin; EA: edge activator.

Characterization and evaluation of the prepared transfersomal dispersion

Entrapment efficiency (EE%)

The entrapment efficiency (EE%) of RIV within the transfersomal vesicles was determined for all formulations (F1–F20). An aliquot of 2 mL from each formulation was placed into an Amicon® ultracentrifugal filter (10 kDa

MWCO, Merck Millipore) and centrifuged using a digital centrifuge (Hettich EBA 20, Germany) at 5000 rpm for 30 min. The filtrate (supernatant containing the free, non-entrapped drug) was collected, suitably diluted with methanol, and analyzed using a UV-visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu, Japan) set at a wavelength of 249 nm (Almehmady and Elsisy 2020). The entrapment efficiency (EE%) was calculated using Equation 1 (Omar et al. 2019):

$$EE\% = \frac{\text{Total quantity of rivaroxaban} - \text{Free quantity of rivaroxaban}}{\text{Total quantity of rivaroxaban}} \times 100 \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where “Total RIV” is the initial amount of drug used in the formulation, and “Free RIV” is the amount quantified in the supernatant.

Drug content evaluation

The drug content of each formulation was determined by accurately diluting 1 mL of transfersomal dispersion (corresponding to 1 mg of RIV) with 10 mL of methanol to disrupt

the vesicles and dissolve RIV completely. The resulting solutions were filtered, and the absorbance was measured using a UV-visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu, Japan) set at a wavelength of 249 nm. RIV concentration was calculated from a previously constructed calibration curve in methanol, and the percentage drug content was expressed relative to the theoretical amount of RIV in each formulation using Equation 2 (Al-Mahmood et al. 2025).

$$\text{Drug content} = \frac{\text{Actual weight of rivaroxaban}}{\text{Theoretical weight of rivaroxaban}} \times 100 \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

pH measurement

The pH of the transfersomal dispersions (F1–F20) was measured using a calibrated digital pH meter (HANNA instruments pH meter, Germany). The electrode was directly immersed in the dispersion, and the reading was recorded after stabilization (approximately 120 s). All measurements were performed at room temperature in triplicate, and the mean \pm SD values were reported (Hussein and Al-Kinani 2025).

Vesicle size and polydispersity index (PDI)

The mean vesicle size and polydispersity index (PDI) of the transfersomal formulations were determined using dynamic light scattering (DLS) with a Zetasizer instrument (Malvern Zetasizer analyzer, Malvern, UK). Before measurement, each dispersion was appropriately diluted with deionized water to obtain suitable scattering intensity. Measurements were performed at 25 °C, and each sample was analyzed in triplicate. The mean vesicle size (nm) and PDI were recorded as mean \pm SD ($n = 3$) (Danaei et al. 2018; Alkufi and Kassab 2025).

In vitro drug release study

The *in vitro* release of RIV from selected transfersomal formulations (F4, F5, and F20) and from RIV suspension was evaluated using the USP dissolution apparatus II (FAITHFUL FRC-6 dissolution tester, China). Dialysis bags (Sigma-Aldrich, MWCO 8000–14000 Da) were pre-soaked in PBS (pH 7.4) overnight and filled with 10 mL of RIV-loaded transfersomal dispersion or RIV suspension equivalent to 10 mg of drug. Each dialysis bag was tightly sealed and immersed in 200 mL of PBS (pH 7.4) containing 1% w/v SLS, maintained at 37 ± 0.5 °C, and stirred at 100 rpm. At predetermined time intervals (0, 0.5, 2, 4, 8, 12, and 24 h), 2 mL samples were withdrawn from the release medium, filtered through a 0.22 μm syringe filter, and analyzed using a UV-visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu, Japan) set at a wavelength of 250 nm. An equal volume (2 mL) of fresh pre-warmed dissolution medium was added to maintain sink conditions. All experiments were conducted in triplicate, and the cumulative percentage of RIV released was plotted as a function of time and assessed according to Equation 3 (Teng et al. 2019; Abdal-Hamid et al. 2025).

$$\text{Release\%} = \frac{\text{Rivaroxaban released}}{\text{Total rivaroxaban}} \times 100 \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

Release kinetics

The *in vitro* release data of RIV from the selected transfersomal formulations were fitted to different kinetic models (Korsmeyer–Peppas, Higuchi, first-order, and zero-order) using DD-Solver, an Excel add-in for dissolution profile analysis. The model providing the highest correlation coefficient (R^2) was considered the best fit. For the Korsmeyer–Peppas model, the release exponent (n) was used to elucidate the prominent drug release mechanism (Cascone 2017).

Choice of the lead transfersomal formulation

The candidate formulations were first screened for high drug content and EE%, acceptable pH, and nanoscale vesicle size with low PDI, followed by comparison of 24 h cumulative release.

Zeta potential (ζ) and deformability index

The zeta potential of the lead transfersomal formulation was measured using a Zetasizer (Malvern Zetasizer, UK) after suitable dilution with deionized water (Al-Mahmood and Rajab 2025). The deformability index (DI) was determined by extruding the dispersion through a 50 nm polycarbonate membrane under vacuum and measuring vesicle sizes before and after extrusion (Zhang et al. 2020). DI was calculated according to Equation 4:

$$\text{Deformability Index (DI)} = J_x \frac{rv}{rp} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

where J is the amount of vesicle suspension extruded per unit time (mL/min), rv is the vesicle size before extrusion (nm), and rp is the pore diameter of the membrane (nm).

Field-emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM)

FESEM (Inspect F, FEI Company, USA) was used to image the pure drug and the vesicles. FESEM utilizes a field-emission gun as an electron source, which provides a more stable and high-brightness beam. Such a beam is characterized by lower currents; thus, less heat is produced, and sample damage is reduced. A drop from the lead transfersomal dispersion was spread over double-sided conductive carbon tape and platinum coating. The images of the sample were captured at an accelerating voltage of 15 kV (Gardouh et al. 2019).

Lyophilization of the transfersomes

The lead RIV-loaded transfersomal dispersion was lyophilized using a freeze dryer (Labconco FreeZone Benchtop Freeze Dryer, Germany). Preparation of the lyophilized material started by dissolving mannitol at a 3% concentration in the transfersomal dispersion, which contained 100 mg of the drug. The resultant mixture was frozen initially at $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 2 h and, afterward, sublimated at $-40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 1 h. Finally, it was kept at $-15\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 8 h, and then the final lyophilized product was stored at $3\text{--}8\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for further studies (Zhang et al. 2022).

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

The compatibility between the drug and excipient was evaluated using Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (Shimadzu, Japan). Evaluations were determined between the FTIR spectra of RIV, the physical mixture of the lead transfersomal components, and the lyophilized powder of the lead transfersomal dispersion design. The samples were compressed into a disc using KBr as the medium. Later, the samples were investigated within the range of $4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ using a scanning technique (Eisa et al. 2022).

Thermal analysis

A differential scanning calorimeter (DSC) is the instrument utilized for providing information on thermal behavior and any interactions between sample components. Analysis by DSC (DSC-60 Plus, Shimadzu, Japan) was performed for pure RIV, the physical mixture of the lead transfersomal formulation components, and the lyophilized powder of the lead transfersomal formulation. Two aluminum pans were used: a reference (empty) pan and a sample pan. The temperature was elevated at a heating rate of $5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ from 25 to $250\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ with purging nitrogen gas, after which thermograms were analyzed (Noor and Ghareeb 2020).

Powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD)

The crystalline structure of the material can be evaluated using PXRD (Shimadzu XRD-6000, Japan). The diffractograms of RIV raw material and the lyophilized powder of the lead formulation were evaluated. The measurement was performed at 2θ between 10 and 100 degrees, with a persistent scan at an operating voltage of 40 kV and a current of 30 mA (Abdullah and Khalid 2023).

Ex vivo transdermal permeation study

The *ex vivo* permeation of RIV from the lead transfersomal formulation and from the RIV suspension was evaluated using excised rat abdominal skin mounted on Franz diffusion cells (Vertical Diffusion Cell System: HDT-1000, Copley) (Todo 2017). Three Wistar albino rats ($\sim 250\text{ g}$) were used, which were obtained from the Animal House of the College of Pharmacy, University of Baghdad. The study adhered to ethical guidelines approved by the Research Ethics Committee of the College of Pharmacy, University of Baghdad (protocol code RECO32429A, date: 15 October 2024). The rats were euthanized, and full-thick-

ness abdominal skin was carefully excised, cleaned of adhering fat, and equilibrated in PBS (pH 7.4). The skin was mounted between the donor and receptor compartments, with the stratum corneum facing the donor side. The receptor compartment was filled with 25 mL of PBS (pH 7.4) containing 1% w/v SLS and maintained at $37 \pm 0.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ under continuous stirring. An accurately measured amount of formulation (1 mL) equivalent to 1 mg of RIV was applied to the donor compartment. At predetermined time intervals ($0.5, 1, 2, 4, 6,$ and 8 h), 1 mL samples were withdrawn from the receptor medium and immediately replaced with an equal volume of fresh PBS (pH 7.4 + 1% SLS) to maintain sink conditions (Fan et al. 2022). Samples were analyzed using a UV-visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu, Japan) set at a wavelength of 250 nm to determine the cumulative amount of RIV permeated per unit area ($Q, \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$) (Bezrouk et al. 2017). The effective diffusion area of the Franz diffusion cell was 3.14 cm^2 . The software package SAMPA version 1.04 was employed to calculate the permeation parameters in the study of skin and membrane permeation data. The primary objective of the SAMPA methodology was to remove uncertainty in the calculation process, since it had the potential to present variation in the data pertaining to skin penetration. The permeation profile was obtained by plotting the cumulative amount of RIV ($Q, \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$) that penetrated through the rat skin on the Y-axis against the corresponding time (in h) on the X-axis. The plot was used for the determination of permeation parameters, specifically the transdermal flux of RIV at steady state ($JSS, \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2/\text{h}$). Transdermal flux was calculated by determining the slope of the linear portion of the regression line. The lag time ($Tlag$) was determined by calculating the intercept of the regression line with the X-axis. The permeability coefficient ($Kp, \text{cm}/\text{h}$) was calculated by dividing the transdermal flux across the vertical Franz diffusion cell (JSS) by the initial concentration (Co) of RIV in the donor compartment ($1\text{ mg}/\text{mL}$) (Equation 5) (Abdulameer and Maraie 2025).

$$\text{Permeability coefficient (Kp)} = \frac{JSS}{Co} \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

where JSS is the transdermal flux across the vertical Franz diffusion cell and Co is the initial concentration of RIV ($1\text{ mg}/\text{mL}$) in the donor compartment.

Histopathological evaluation of rat skin following transdermal application of the selected RIV transfersomal formula

At the end of the 72 h transdermal application period, six male Wistar rats were humanely euthanized, and full-thickness skin samples were excised and prepared for histological evaluation to assess potential dermal irritation. Each specimen was preserved individually in 10% neutral buffered formalin, pH 7.4 (Sampedro-Carrillo 2021). The samples were processed through a graded ethanol series for dehydration, then paraffin-embedded and trimmed into vertical sections measuring $5\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ in thickness. The resulting sections were stained with hematoxylin and eosin (H&E)

and examined under a light microscope (Imam et al. 2017). The treated skin samples were compared to those obtained from untreated healthy control rats, with particular attention given to evidence of inflammatory cell infiltration or other histological indicators of irritation. Before treatment, the hair on the dorsal surface of each rat was removed 24 h before the study. The lead transfersomal formulation was evenly applied over a 4 cm² area of the shaved skin.

Stability study

The lead transfersomal formulation was stored in tightly sealed vials and subjected to two distinct storage conditions: refrigerator temperature (4 ± 2 °C) and room temperature (25 ± 2 °C). This storage was maintained for a duration of 3 months (Abdulameer and Maraie 2025). The entrapment efficiency, vesicle size, pH, and drug content were re-evaluated every month.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using GraphPad Prism software (version 10). To evaluate the effects of formulation variables, the datasets were divided into specific comparison families. First, one-way ANOVA was used to compare the effect of different edge activator types (Soluplus, Span 65, Span 80, and Tween 20) at constant lecithin:edge activator ratios. Second, separate one-way ANOVAs were conducted to assess the effect of varying the edge activator concentration (5% to 25%) within each individual edge activator series. For all ANOVAs, Tukey's post hoc test was applied for pairwise comparisons to identify specific significant differences between the selected formulations. A *p*-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. All measurements were performed in independent triplicates (*n* = 3), and data are presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) (Abdulameer and Maraie 2025).

Results and discussion

Lambda maximum (λ max) of rivaroxaban

Scanning of a solution containing 10 μ g/mL of RIV in methanol and PBS pH 7.4 + 1% w/v SLS by UV-visible spectrophotometer (Shimadzu, Japan) at 200–400 nm resulted in a lambda maximum (λ max) of 249 nm in meth-

anol and 250 nm in PBS pH 7.4 + 1% w/v SLS, as shown in Fig. 1, which was close to the reported λ max of RIV (Çelebier et al. 2014).

Calibration curve of rivaroxaban

The calibration curves of RIV in methanol and in PBS pH 7.4 + 1% w/v SLS are shown in Fig. 2. A straight line was obtained by plotting the absorbance versus the concentration. The result indicated that the calibration curves obeyed Beer's law within the range of concentrations used.

Entrapment efficiency (EE %)

The entrapment efficiency of RIV within the prepared transfersomal formulations (F1–F20) ranged from 84.3% \pm 0.6 to 98.9% \pm 1.05 (Table 2). All formulations demonstrated a high EE percentage (>84%), indicating the suitability of the rotary evaporation–sonication method and the selected lipid/edge activator composition for efficient incorporation of the lipophilic anticoagulant within the vesicular systems (Opatha et al. 2020; Raju et al. 2023).

The effect of different types of the edge activators on the entrapment efficiency

Fig. 3 compares formulations at the same lecithin:edge activator percentage but with different edge activator types. Thus, F1, F6, F11, and F16 were compared at 95:5; F2, F7, F12, and F17 at 90:10; F3, F8, F13, and F18 at 85:15; F4, F9,

Table 2. Entrapment efficiency percentage of RIV transfersomal dispersions.

Formulations	EE%	Formulations	EE%
F1	94.8% \pm 1.05	F11	96.9% \pm 0.85
F2	94.9% \pm 0.26	F12	96.9% \pm 1.65
F3	95.6% \pm 1.21	F13	94.9% \pm 0.20
F4	93.6% \pm 0.36	F14	95.6% \pm 2.16
F5	96% \pm 1.0	F15	98.6% \pm 0.52
F6	98.6% \pm 0.95	F16	98.9% \pm 1.05
F7	96.4% \pm 1.21	F17	98% \pm 1.00
F8	92.4% \pm 1.21	F18	93.5% \pm 1.32
F9	87.7% \pm 1.12	F19	92.5% \pm 1.32
F10	84.3% \pm 0.6	F20	84.5% \pm 1.80

Values are presented as mean \pm SD (*n* = 3).

Figure 1. UV spectrum of RIV in: **A.** Methanol and **B.** PBS pH 7.4 + 1% w/v SLS.

Figure 2. Calibration curve of RIV in **A.** Methanol and **B.** PBS pH 7.4 + 1% w/v SLS.

F14, and F19 at 80:20; and F5, F10, F15, and F20 at 75:25. Within each fixed percentage group, one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's test was used to determine whether entrapment efficiency differed significantly among Soluplus, Span 65, Span 80, and Tween 20. All formulations had high EE% ($\approx 84\%$ – 99%), but the mean EE% differed significantly between the four edge activator types (Soluplus, Span 65, Span 80, and Tween 20) at the same lecithin/EA ratios ($p < 0.05$). Soluplus- and Span-based systems, especially F4, F5, F6, F15, F16, and F17, clustered at the upper range of EE%, indicating that the choice of EA type had a statistically significant impact on improving drug entrapment efficiency. This trend aligns with previous findings where non-ionic surfactants, such as Tween 20 or Span

variants, yield high EE% due to their ability to reduce interfacial tension and stabilize the lipid bilayer during vesicle formation, preventing drug leakage (Mohd et al. 2024). Soluplus, an amphiphilic graft copolymer, likely enhances EE% through its dual role as both an EA and solubilizer for poorly water-soluble RIV, similar to reports on Soluplus in nanostructured lipid carriers that improved drug loading via polymer–lipid interactions (Li et al. 2017).

Effect of the percentage of edge activator on the EE %

To assess the effect of edge activator concentration, one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post hoc test was ap-

Figure 3. The EE% of RIV-loaded transfersomes, where **A.** (F1, F6, F11, and F16) lecithin/edge activator 95:5; **B.** (F2, F7, F12, and F17) lecithin/edge activator 90:10; **C.** (F3, F8, F13, and F18) lecithin/edge activator 85:15; **D.** (F4, F9, F14, and F19) lecithin/edge activator 80:20, and **E.** (F5, F10, F15, and F20) lecithin/edge activator 75:25.

plied separately within each edge activator series. Thus, the Soluplus formulations (F1–F5), Span 65 formulations (F6–F10), Span 80 formulations (F11–F15), and Tween 20 formulations (F16–F20) were each compared across the five lecithin:edge activator ratios (95:5, 90:10, 85:15, 80:20, and 75:25) to determine whether increasing edge activator percentage significantly affected entrapment efficiency. As shown in Fig. 4, increasing the EA percentage from 5% to 25% (lecithin/EA ratios 95:5 to 75:25) generally improved EE% within each EA series ($p < 0.05$), with optimal values at 20%–25% for Soluplus (F4: $93.6\% \pm 0.36$; F5: $96\% \pm 1.0$) and Span 80 (F15: $98.6\% \pm 0.52$). This concentration-dependent enhancement is attributed to greater bilayer disruption and increased aqueous compartment availability for drug solubilization at higher EA levels, up to a saturation point where excess EA induces vesicle instability (Rajendran et al. 2026). Tween 20 showed slightly lower EE% at higher ratios, possibly due to increased membrane fluidity causing minor drug expulsion (Pérez-Rosés et al. 2015). Because Span 65 is highly lipophilic (HLB 2.1) and solid, at higher ratios, it tends to separate from the lecithin bilayer and crystallize or

form separate solid lipid domains rather than a flexible vesicular membrane. This phase separation excludes the drug from the vesicle or disrupts the vesicle structure entirely, leading to a significant drop in entrapment, down to 84.3% in F10 (Yeo et al. 2018; Opatha et al. 2020).

Drug content of transfersomal dispersion

All transfersomal formulations (F1–F20) showed high drug content values between $90\% \pm 1.3$ and $99.5\% \pm 0.11$ (Table 3), confirming the uniform distribution of RIV and the reproducibility of the preparation method (Balata et al. 2020).

pH of rivaroxaban transfersomal dispersions

The pH values of the transfersomal dispersions (F1–F20) ranged from 6.25 ± 0.35 to 7.4 ± 0.65 , which lies within the acceptable pH range for topical or transdermal application and is unlikely to cause skin irritation (Daood et al. 2019).

Figure 4. The EE% of RIV-loaded transfersomes: **A.** Represents Soluplus-based transfersomes (F1, F2, F3, F4, and F5); **B.** Represents Span 65-based transfersomes (F6, F7, F8, F9, and F10); **C.** Represents Span 80-based transfersomes (F11, F12, F13, F14, and F15); **D.** Represents Tween 20-based transfersomes (F16, F17, F18, F19, and F20).

Vesicle size and polydispersity index of the transfersomal dispersions

The mean vesicle size of the formulations (F1–F20) ranged from 89.36 ± 1.1 nm to 256.5 ± 1.3 nm, with PDI values between 0.1164 ± 0.005 and 0.393 ± 0.034 , indicating nanosized vesicles with narrow to moderately broad size distributions, reflecting a homogeneous population of nanosized, well-dispersed vesicles, which is favorable for transdermal permeation (Qushawy et al. 2018).

Effect of different types of edge activators on the particle size

To assess the effect of edge activator type at the same lecithin:edge activator ratio, formulations were compared within each fixed percentage group. Accordingly, F1, F6,

F11, and F16 were compared at 95:5; F2, F7, F12, and F17 at 90:10; F3, F8, F13, and F18 at 85:15; F4, F9, F14, and F19 at 80:20; and F5, F10, F15, and F20 at 75:25. One-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post hoc test was used to identify significant differences among the four edge activator types within each percentage group. Fig. 5 demonstrates that EA type profoundly affects mean vesicle size ($p < 0.05$), with Soluplus (F1–F5: 96–135 nm) and Tween 20 (F16–F20: 89–188 nm) producing significantly smaller vesicles than Span 65 (F6–F10: 104–256 nm) or Span 80 (F11–F15: 112–195 nm). Smaller sizes with Soluplus and Tween 20 result from their higher HLB values (≈ 15 – 16), which promote finer lipid film hydration and sonication-induced size reduction via enhanced bilayer fluidity. Span 65 (HLB 2.1) and Span 80 (HLB 4.3), being more lipophilic, initially form larger and less deformable aggregates (Wongsirojkul et al. 2025).

Table 3. Drug content percentage, pH, vesicle size, and polydispersity index results of RIV-loaded transfersomal dispersion formulations.

Formulation	Drug content %	pH	Vesicle size (nm)	Polydispersity index
F1	90 ± 1.30	6.62 ± 0.33	135 ± 2.0	0.3499 ± 0.005
F2	95 ± 0.80	7.03 ± 0.57	119.4 ± 1.9	0.1504 ± 0.008
F3	93 ± 0.57	6.64 ± 0.32	113.1 ± 2.7	0.1983 ± 0.009
F4	97 ± 0.43	6.69 ± 0.76	98.36 ± 2.0	0.1164 ± 0.005
F5	98 ± 0.75	6.71 ± 0.28	96.67 ± 1.5	0.1444 ± 0.0007
F6	95.1 ± 0.66	6.25 ± 0.35	256.5 ± 1.3	0.2838 ± 0.030
F7	96.3 ± 0.80	6.52 ± 0.65	208.9 ± 2.8	0.2413 ± 0.001
F8	97 ± 0.66	6.65 ± 1.20	138.9 ± 3.4	0.251 ± 0.010
F9	98.5 ± 0.20	6.71 ± 0.80	124.8 ± 1.3	0.232 ± 0.019
F10	99.2 ± 0.35	7.33 ± 0.55	104.1 ± 3.4	0.1557 ± 0.003
F11	99.5 ± 0.11	6.56 ± 0.65	194.7 ± 1.5	0.3583 ± 0.007
F12	95.3 ± 0.23	6.5 ± 0.29	160.2 ± 2.3	0.393 ± 0.034
F13	96.4 ± 0.55	6.36 ± 0.12	123.7 ± 1.4	0.2653 ± 0.017
F14	98 ± 0.33	7.4 ± 0.65	119.9 ± 2.1	0.2155 ± 0.012
F15	99.3 ± 0.12	7.3 ± 0.77	112.3 ± 3.1	0.2299 ± 0.009
F16	98.8 ± 0.65	6.77 ± 1.3	188 ± 2.6	0.3322 ± 0.006
F17	98.1 ± 0.25	6.39 ± 0.44	157.3 ± 2.1	0.2577 ± 0.020
F18	95 ± 0.67	7.2 ± 0.85	123 ± 2.6	0.2391 ± 0.008
F19	97.3 ± 0.90	7.3 ± 0.12	111.1 ± 1.0	0.2164 ± 0.014
F20	99 ± 0.60	6.65 ± 0.60	89.36 ± 1.1	0.172 ± 0.008

Values are presented as mean ± SD ($n = 3$).

Figure 5. The particle sizes of RIV-loaded transfersomes were **A.** (F1, F6, F11, and F16) lecithin/edge activator 95:5; **B.** (F2, F7, F12, and F17) lecithin/edge activator 90:10; **C.** (F3, F8, F13, and F18) lecithin/edge activator 85:15; **D.** (F4, F9, F14, and F19) lecithin/edge activator 80:20, and **E.** (F5, F10, F15, and F20) lecithin/edge activator 75:25.

Effect of percentage of edge activator on the particle size

Within each edge activator type, one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post hoc test was applied to the Soluplus series (F1–F5), Span 65 series (F6–F10), Span

80 series (F11–F15), and Tween 20 series (F16–F20) across the five ratios (95:5 to 75:25) to evaluate the effect of edge activator percentage within the same type of edge activator. Fig. 6 illustrates that, within each EA type, increasing EA% from 5% to 25% significantly decreases vesicle size ($p < 0.05$). This indicates a statistically signif-

Figure 6. Particle size of RIV-loaded transfersomes: A. Represents Soluplus-based transfersomes (F1, F2, F3, F4, and F5); B. Represents Span 65-based transfersomes (F6, F7, F8, F9, and F10); C. Represents Span 80-based transfersomes (F11, F12, F13, F14, and F15); D. Represents Tween 20-based transfersomes (F16, F17, F18, F19, and F20).

icant dose–response relationship, where higher EA levels enhance bilayer flexibility and reduce vesicle size (Jahan et al. 2025).

Effect of different types of edge activators on the polydispersity index

Fig. 7 compares PDI across edge activator types at fixed lecithin:edge activator ratios. Thus, F1, F6, F11, and F16 were analyzed at 95:5; F2, F7, F12, and F17 at 90:10; F3, F8, F13, and F18 at 85:15; F4, F9, F14, and F19 at 80:20; and F5, F10, F15, and F20 at 75:25. One-way ANOVA with Tukey's test confirmed significant differences ($p < 0.05$), with Soluplus and Tween 20 yielding lower PDI than Span variants. Soluplus and Tween 20 formulations exhibited the lowest PDI values (0.11–0.18, $p < 0.05$), indicating more homogeneous vesicle populations than Span 65 and Span 80 (0.23–0.39). Low PDI reflects uniform bilayer disruption by high-HLB edge activators, minimizing polydisperse aggregates during hydration (El Zaafrany et al. 2010).

Effect of the percentage of edge activator on the PDI

Fig. 8 shows PDI within each edge activator series across ratios. The Soluplus series (F1–F5), Span 65 series (F6–F10), Span 80 series (F11–F15), and Tween 20 series (F16–F20) were analyzed separately by one-way ANOVA with Tukey's test ($p < 0.05$), revealing a concentration-dependent PDI reduction. At certain edge activator percentages, such as Soluplus 20% in F4, the PDI reached very low values (~0.116), statistically indicating highly uniform nanovesicles, while suboptimal edge activator levels showed significantly higher PDI (Kharwade et al. 2023).

In vitro drug release of transfersomal dispersion

The *in vitro* release profiles of RIV from the selected transfersomal formulations (F4, F5, and F20) and from RIV suspension over 24 h are shown in Fig. 9. All transfersomal

Figure 7. PDI of RIV-loaded transfersomes were A. (F1, F6, F11, and F16) lecithin/edge activator 95:5; B. (F2, F7, F12, and F17) lecithin/edge activator 90:10; C. (F3, F8, F13, and F18) lecithin/edge activator 85:15; D. (F4, F9, F14, and F19) lecithin/edge activator 80:20, and E. (F5, F10, F15, and F20) lecithin/edge activator 75:25.

formulations exhibited a biphasic pattern characterized by an initial faster release phase during the first 4 h, followed by a more gradual release up to 24 h, whereas the suspension showed a slow, almost linear increase over time (Balata et al. 2020). After 24 h, F4 achieved the highest cumulative release ($97.8\% \pm 0.72$), followed by F5 ($91.0\% \pm 1.0$), while the Tween 20-based formulation F20 showed lower release ($75.0\% \pm 2.64$); in contrast, the RIV suspension released only $13.0\% \pm 0.5$ of the drug over the same period ($n = 3$). The differences between all transfersomal formulations and the suspension were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), and F4 also released significantly more RIV than F20 at 24 h ($p < 0.05$). The release from Soluplus-based transfersomes (F4 and F5) compared with the Tween 20-based system (F20) and the suspension can be attributed to the amphiphilic nature of Soluplus, which lowers interfacial tension, enhances RIV solubilization within the vesicular matrix, and increases bilayer fluidity, thereby facilitating drug diffusion into the dissolution medium (Obaidat et al. 2019).

Kinetics of drug release

To gain further insight into the release mechanism, the release data of F4, F5, and F20 were fitted to zero-order, first-order, Higuchi, and Korsmeyer–Peppas models using DD-Solver (Table 4). For the Soluplus-based formulations F4 and F5, the first-order model provided the highest correlation coefficients ($R^2 = 0.9908$ and 0.9905 , respectively), indicating that first-order kinetics best describes their overall release behavior, whereas for F20, the Korsmeyer–Peppas and Higuchi models showed the best fit ($R^2 = 0.9997$ and 0.9978 , respectively). The first-order model is the statistically preferred model for F4 and F5, with the Korsmeyer–Peppas exponents ($n < 0.5$ for all three formulations), which support the conclusion that drug transport is predominantly Fickian diffusion-controlled rather than anomalous or erosion-controlled (Wójcik-Pastuszka et al. 2019).

Figure 8. PDI of RIV-loaded transferosomes, where **A.** Represents Soluplus-based transferosomes (F1, F2, F3, F4, and F5); **B.** Represents Span 65-based transferosomes (F6, F7, F8, F9, and F10); **C.** Represents Span 80-based transferosomes (F11, F12, F13, F14, and F15), and **D.** Represents Tween 20-based transferosomes (F16, F17, F18, F19, and F20).

Table 4. Kinetic modeling of the drug release profile of F4, F5, and F20.

Formulations	Zero order R^2	First order R^2	Higuchi model R^2	Korsmeyer–Peppas model $R^2 - N$	
F4	0.6104	0.9908	0.9737	0.9802	0.443
F5	0.7214	0.9905	0.9872	0.9872	0.496
F20	0.6954	0.9261	0.9978	0.9997	0.468

The lead transfersomal dispersion formula

Among the 20 investigated formulations, F4 (Soluplus-based, lecithin/edge activator ratio 80:20) was selected as the lead transfersomal formulation because it provided the most favorable overall balance of critical quality attributes. Specifically, F4 combined high entrapment efficiency ($93.6\% \pm 0.36$) and drug content ($97.0\% \pm 0.43$) with nano-sized vesicles (98.36 ± 2.0 nm) and the lowest polydispersity index (0.1164 ± 0.005) among all formulations, together with a suitable pH (6.69 ± 0.76) for transdermal application. In addition, F4 exhibited near-complete cumulative release of RIV after 24 h ($97.8\% \pm 0.72$), outperforming the Soluplus-based formulation F5 ($91.0\% \pm 1.0$) and Tween

20-based formulation F20 ($75.0\% \pm 2.64$) under the same conditions. Taken together, these findings justify the selection of F4 as the lead formulation for subsequent physico-chemical characterization and *ex vivo* permeation studies.

Zeta potential (ζ) and deformability index

Zeta potential (ζ) is an essential factor for assessing the stability of transferosomes (Anggraini et al. 2017). The zeta potential of -24.16 mV for F4 indicates moderate electrostatic repulsion between vesicles, which, together with the low PDI, supports excellent physical stability of the dispersion during storage (Danaei et al. 2018). The calculated deformability index for the lead transfersomal formulation F4 was 9.6 ± 0.34 , which indicates excellent vesicular de-

Figure 9. The cumulative release percentage of RIV from transfersomal formulations F4, F5, and F20 compared to that of RIV suspension.

formability. This property reveals their ability to traverse through layers of the skin while retaining the integrity of the vesicles (Alkufi and Kassab 2025).

Surface morphology by scanning electron microscopy (FESEM)

The surface morphology of the pure drug and the lead transfersomal formulation (F4) was established by FESEM, as shown in Fig. 10. The shape of the pure drug was crystalline, while the shape of the lead transfersomal formulation (F4) was spherical and nanosized, demonstrating the appropriateness of the employed components and method (Abdulameer and Maraie 2025).

Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy

FTIR spectra are frequently used to identify possible drug–excipient incompatibility. Fig. 11 represents the FTIR spectra of RIV powder, the physical mixture of all F4 components, and the FTIR spectrum of the lyophilized powder of the lead transfersomal formulation (F4). FTIR of RIV powder showed characteristic bands located at 3354 cm^{-1} corresponding to secondary amide (N-H) stretching, 1751 cm^{-1} corresponding to C=O stretching, 1643 cm^{-1} corresponding to amide stretching, 1514 cm^{-1} corresponding to Ar-Cl stretching, 1340 cm^{-1} corresponding to C-O-C movement, and $825\text{--}543\text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponding to C-Cl stretching (Shaligram et al. 2025). The FTIR spectra of the lyophilized powder of the selected formula (F4) displayed the characteristic FTIR bands corresponding to RIV, however, with a significant decrease in intensity, suggesting molecular dispersion of the drug within the lipid–polymer matrix rather than chemical degradation, which indicated that there was no unfavorable interaction between RIV and the excipients combined in the formulation.

Thermal analysis

Pure RIV, the physical mixture of the F4 components, which consisted of RIV, Soluplus, and lecithin, as well as the lyophilized powder of the lead transfersomal formu-

lation (F4), were analyzed by DSC. Fig. 12 shows the DSC of RIV, which exhibited an endothermic peak at $233.38\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for RIV, corresponding to the melting temperature of the reference, which indicated the purity of the crystalline drug and agreed with the reported values (Shaligram et al. 2025). DSC of the physical mixture of F4 components showed three endothermic peaks: $76.37\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $218.42\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and $231.48\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, representing Soluplus, lecithin, and RIV, respectively. The DSC thermogram of the lyophilized powder of F4 indicated the disappearance or broadening of the sharp melting endotherm of crystalline RIV in the lyophilized transfersomes, pointing to partial amorphization and successful entrapment of the drug within the vesicular structure. The endothermic peak was seen at $149\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ due to the melting of mannitol, which was added before the lyophilization of the transfersomal dispersion (Jakubowska et al. 2022).

Powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD)

The powder X-ray diffraction analysis for pure RIV and lyophilized powder of the selected formula F4 was studied, as shown in Fig. 13. PXRD patterns further confirmed the reduction in crystallinity, which can contribute to improving the apparent solubility and dissolution rate of RIV from the transfersomal system (Shaligram et al. 2025).

Transdermal permeation study of rivaroxaban transfersomal formulations

Ex vivo permeation profiles of RIV from the lead transfersomal formulation F4 and from RIV suspension across excised rat abdominal skin are shown in Fig. 14 and Table 5. Formulation F4 achieved a cumulative permeated amount of $261.146 \pm 6.7\text{ }\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ after 8 h, corresponding to approximately $82\% \pm 2.5\text{ }\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ of the applied dose, whereas RIV suspension reached only $47.77 \pm 0.7\text{ }\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ ($15.086\% \pm 0.3$) over the same period ($p < 0.05$). The steady-state flux (JSS) and permeability coefficient (KP) of RIV from F4 ($88.411\text{ }\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2/\text{h}$ and $0.0884\text{ cm}/\text{h}$, respectively) were markedly higher than those of the RIV suspension ($11.934\text{ }\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2/\text{h}$ and $0.0119\text{ cm}/\text{h}$). Moreover, the lag time for F4 (0.258 h) was significantly shorter than that of the suspension (0.425 h). The results further demonstrated the enhanced *ex vivo* performance

Table 5. Cumulative amount permeated of RIV (Q , $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$) from F4 and RIV suspension.

Time (h)	Amount permeated $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ of F4	Amount permeated $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ of RIV suspension
0.5	22.292 ± 4	1.91 ± 0.1
1	63.694 ± 4.5	6.369 ± 1
2	149.681 ± 6	19.515 ± 4
4	222.929 ± 7.9	35.668 ± 6
6	254.777 ± 8	43.949 ± 7
8	261.146 ± 6.7	47.77 ± 0.7

Values are presented as mean \pm SD ($n = 3$).

Figure 10. FESEM of A. Pure RIV and B. The selected RIV-loaded transfersomal dispersion (F4).

Figure 11. FTIR of RIV powder, physical mixture of all F4 components, and FTIR of lyophilized powder of the selected formula (F4).

Figure 13. PXRD of pure RIV and the lyophilized powder of selected formulation F4.

Figure 12. DSC of pure RIV, physical mixture of all F4 components, and lyophilized powder of F4.

Figure 14. Permeation profiles of RIV from its suspension and F4.

of the lead transfersomal formulation F4 compared to the RIV suspension. F4 achieved approximately a 5.5-fold higher cumulative permeation and a markedly higher transdermal flux, together with a shorter lag time. These findings highlight the combined effect of nanoscale vesicle size, high deformability index (DI =

9.6), and the presence of Soluplus as an edge activator in enhancing skin permeation. Flexible transfersomes squeeze through intercellular lipid channels of the stratum corneum under the influence of the transdermal hydration gradient, thereby overcoming one of the main limitations of conventional liposomes in transdermal drug delivery (Ahad et al. 2017).

Histopathological examination of rat skin following transdermal application of the selected transfersomal formula

Fig. 15 presents light photomicrographs of rat skin cross-sections after 72 h of administration of the selected transfersomal formula, stained with hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) at 100× magnification, and the untreated healthy control rat skin cross-section. The histopathological figure of the untreated healthy control rat skin (Fig. 15A) revealed the normal appearance of epidermis-lining epithelial cells and a normal keratin layer and the normal appearance of dermal collagen fibers with fibroblast and fibrocyte contents; the dermis showed hair follicles with related sebaceous glands. Fig. 15B exhibited preserved epidermal and dermal structures with no visible signs of irritation, ulceration, or inflammatory cell infiltration. The tissue morphology appeared comparable to that of the untreated control.

Stability study of rivaroxaban-loaded transfersomal dispersion

The entrapment efficiency and vesicle size of RIV-loaded transfersomal dispersions were examined under refrigerated (4 ± 2 °C) and room temperature (25 ± 2 °C) conditions over 1, 2, and 3 months, as presented in Table 6. The findings indicated a statistically non-significant reduction in entrapment efficiency and a slight, non-significant rise in vesicle diameter throughout the 3-month period ($p > 0.05$). The gradual enlargement of transfersomal vesicles

is probably attributable to coalescence phenomena arising from weak van der Waals and cohesive forces within the vesicles (Salem et al. 2019). Furthermore, pH levels exhibited stability throughout the trial, showing no substantial fluctuation (Syarifah et al. 2021), in alignment with results from a prior inquiry on capsaicin transfersome stability (Aulia 2023). A slight decrease in drug content was observed, although it lacked statistical significance. The stability assessment verified that the F4 transfersomal formulation maintained stability, exhibiting no significant physicochemical changes during the storage duration.

Conclusion

In this study, RIV-loaded transfersomal dispersions were developed and systematically characterized. Among the investigated formulations, F4 (Soluplus-based transfersomes) with a lecithin/edge activator ratio of 80:20 demonstrated high entrapment efficiency, near-complete drug content, nanosized vesicles with a low polydispersity index, suitable pH, and acceptable zeta potential and deformability index. The lead transfersomal formulation (F4) provided a biphasic yet sustained *in vitro* release profile and markedly enhanced *ex vivo* skin permeation, achieving higher cumulative permeation, steady-state flux, and permeability coefficient than the RIV suspension. FTIR, DSC, PXRD, and FESEM analyses confirmed incorporation of RIV into a stable, partially amorphous, nanovesicular system without major drug–excipient incompatibilities.

Figure 15. Histopathological examination of rat skin using H&E staining at 100× magnification: **A.** Untreated control skin. Section of skin (control) shows normal epidermis keratinized lining epithelium (red arrows), normal hair follicle (black arrow) with sebaceous gland (S), and normal dermis fibrous tissue (asterisk). H&E stain. 100×; **B.** Skin treated with the selected transfersomal formula. Section of skin treated with the selected transfersomal formula shows normal epidermis keratinized lining epithelium (red arrows), normal hair follicle (black arrow) with sebaceous gland (S), and normal dermis fibrous tissue (asterisk). H&E stain. 100×.

Table 6. Stability study for the selected transfersomal dispersion formula (F4) under different temperatures (4 ± 2 °C and 25 ± 2 °C).

Parameter	Initial	4 ± 2 °C			25 ± 2 °C		
		Month 1	Month 2	Month 3	Month 1	Month 2	Month 3
EE%	93.6 ± 0.36	93.5 ± 0.11	93.5 ± 0.25	93.44 ± 0.34	93.6 ± 0.44	93.4 ± 0.22	93.33 ± 0.12
Vesicle size	98.36 ± 2	98.77 ± 0.24	99 ± 0.33	99.2 ± 0.12	98.5 ± 0.11	98.6 ± 0.55	99.1 ± 0.3
pH	6.69 ± 0.76	7 ± 0.12	7 ± 0.18	7.1 ± 0.22	6.9 ± 0.66	6.9 ± 0.45	7 ± 0.69
Drug content	97 ± 0.43	97 ± 0.66	97 ± 0.98	96.5 ± 0.55	97 ± 0.45	97 ± 0.88	96 ± 0.87

Values are presented as mean \pm SD ($n = 3$).

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

Experiments on animals: The study adhered to ethical guidelines approved by the Research Ethics Committee of the College of Pharmacy, University of Baghdad (protocol code RE-CO32429A, date: 15 October 2024).

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

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Author contributions

Hussein ZK and Abdal-Hamid SN Conceived and designed the study; Hussein ZK formulation, analysis and interpretation of results; Abdal-Hamid SN supervision and review. Both authors reviewed the results and approved the final version of the manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

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Supplementary material 1

Rivaroxaban -loaded transfersomes compositions

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Data type: xlsx

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Supplementary material 2

Entrapment efficiency percentage of rivaroxaban transfersomal dispersions

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Data type: xlsx

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Supplementary material 3

Drug content percentage, pH, vesicle size, and polydispersity index results of rivaroxaban-loaded transfersomal dispersion formulations

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Data type: xlsx

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Supplementary material 4

Kinetic modeling of drug release profile of F4, F5, and F20

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Data type: xlsx

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Supplementary material 5

Permeability parameters of RIV from RIV suspension and F4

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Supplementary material 6

Stability study for the selected transfersomal dispersion formula (F4) under different temperature (4 ± 2 °C and 25 ± 2 °C)

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Data type: xlsx

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Supplementary material 7

SAMPA software PDF of F4

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Data type: pdf

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Supplementary material 8

SAMPA software PDF of Rivaroxaban suspension

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